

Psychosocial risks in informal workers in the agroindustrial sector in the municipality of Santo Tomás (Colombian Caribbean)

Riesgos psicosociales en trabajadores informales del sector agroindustrial en el municipio de Santo Tomás (Caribe Colombiano)

Riscos psicossociais em trabalhadores informais do setor agroindustrial no município de Santo Tomás (Caribe Colombiano)

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Abstract - Fasecolda assures that there are currently 16 companies in the municipality of Santo Tomas belonging to the agriculture, livestock, hunting, forestry and fishing sector; Similarly, Fasecolda does not have records of work accidents, work-related illnesses or deaths in the last five years in the municipality's agro-industrial sector, so we can deduce that there are many informal workers working in this sector, therefore, since it is not are affiliated with the general occupational risk system, it is not possible to evidence ATEL reports in the occupational risk administrators. Therefore, the general objective of this article is to determine the psychosocial risks in workers in the agroindustrial sector of the municipality of Santo Tomas/Atlántico in the period 2023, through a quantitative, descriptive approach methodology. cross-sectional design, field study with primary source, where the Psychosocial Risk Assessment Questionnaire at Work instrument was applied to a representative sample of 60 informal workers from the agroindustrial sector of Santo Tomas, Atlántico, and is given as the main conclusion that the qualification of informal workers in the agroindustrial sector of Santo Tomas, Atlántico in the dimension Psychological demands, the risk is medium; In the dimension Active work and possibility of development, the risk is medium; in the dimension Social support in business the risk is high; in the Company Compensation dimension the risk is medium; and in the Double presence in company dimension the risk is medium.

Keywords: agrarian economy, job security, work environment, quality of work life, mental health.

Resumen – Fasecolda, asegura que actualmente se encuentran 16 empresas en el municipio de Santo Tomas pertenecientes al sector de agricultura, ganadería, caza, silvicultura y pesca; de igual forma Fasecolda no tiene registros de accidentes de trabajo, enfermedades laborales ni muertes en los últimos cinco años en el sector agroindustrial del municipio, por lo que podemos deducir que

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se encuentran muchos trabajadores informales laborando en este sector, por lo tanto como no se encuentran afiliados al sistema general de riesgos laborales, no es posible evidenciar reportes de ATEL en las administradoras de riesgos laborales. Por lo cual el objetivo general de este artículo es determinar los riesgos psicosociales en los trabajadores del sector agroindustrial del municipio de Santo Tomas/Atlántico en el periodo 2023, a través de metodología de enfoque cuantitativo, de tipo descriptivo. de diseño trasversal, de estudio de campo con fuente primaria, donde a una muestra representativa de 60 trabajadores informales del sector agroindustrial de Santo Tomas, Atlántico, se le aplico el instrumento Cuestionario de Evaluación de Riesgos Psicosociales en el Trabajo, y se da como principal conclusión que la calificación en los trabajadores informales del sector agroindustrial de Santo Tomas, Atlántico en la dimensión Exigencias psicológicas el riesgo es medio; en la dimensión Trabajo activo y posibilidad de desarrollo el riesgo es medio; en la dimensión Apoyo social en empresa el riesgo es alto; en la dimensión Compensaciones en empresa el riesgo es medio; y en la dimensión Doble presencia en empresa el riesgo es medio.

Palabras clave: economía agraria, seguridad en el trabajo, ambiente de trabajo, calidad de la vida laboral, salud mental.

Resumo – A Fasecolda assegura que existem actualmente no concelho de Santo Tomas 16 empresas pertencentes aos sectores da agricultura, pecuária, caça, silvicultura e pesca; Da mesma forma, a Fasecolda não possui registros de acidentes de trabalho, doenças profissionais ou óbitos nos últimos cinco anos no setor agroindustrial do município, portanto podemos deduzir que existem muitos trabalhadores informais trabalhando neste setor, portanto, por ser não estão vinculados ao sistema geral de riscos ocupacionais, não é possível comprovar relatórios ATEL nas administradoras de riscos ocupacionais. Portanto, o objetivo geral deste artigo é determinar os riscos psicossociais em trabalhadores do setor agroindustrial do município de Santo Tomas/Atlántico no período de 2023, através de uma metodologia de abordagem quantitativa, descritiva. desenho transversal, estudo de campo com fonte primária, onde o instrumento Questionário de Avaliação de Risco Psicossocial no Trabalho foi aplicado a uma amostra representativa de 60 trabalhadores informais do setor agroindustrial de Santo Tomas, Atlántico, e tem como principal conclusão que a qualificação dos trabalhadores informais do setor agroindustrial de Santo Tomas, Atlántico na dimensão Demandas psicológicas, o risco é médio; Na dimensão Trabalho ativo e possibilidade de desenvolvimento o risco é médio; na dimensão Apoio social nas empresas o risco é elevado; na dimensão Remuneração da Empresa o risco é médio; e na dimensão Dupla presença na empresa o risco é médio.

Palavras-chave: economia agrária, segurança no trabalho, ambiente de trabalho, qualidade de vida no trabalho, saúde mental.

Introduction

In the municipality of Santo Tomás, located in the department of Atlántico, various agroeconomic activities are developed that contribute significantly to the local economy. Among these activities that stand out according to the mayor of Santo Tomas (2023) are fish farming, pig farming and the cultivation of lemons, as well as other fruits. Pisciculture, which consists of raising fish in ponds or controlled bodies of water, is an important source of income for the inhabitants of the region.

On the other hand, pig farming, dedicated to pig breeding and production, also plays a fundamental role in generating employment and wealth in the area. Furthermore, the cultivation of lemons and other fruits, taking advantage of the favorable climatic conditions of the region, constitutes an important agricultural activity that diversifies production and promotes local food security. These agroeconomic activities reflect the variety and potential of the agricultural sector in Saint Thomas, contributing to sustainable development and community well-being. The mayor of Santo Tomas also tells us that a large part of the agricultural companies are small, since they are made up of less than 49 workers.

According to a Fasescolda report, in 2019 only two registered companies in the agroindustrial sector were found, and in 2020 only 3 registered companies were found, in 2021 there were 7 companies and in 2022 the increase in registered companies could be observed. which for this period there are 17, likewise Fasescolda (2023), assures that there are currently 16 companies in the municipality of Santo Tomas belonging to the agriculture, livestock, hunting, forestry and fishing sector; and reports that 48 workers in the agroindustrial sector are registered in the municipality of Santo Tomas, likewise Fasescolda has no records of work accidents, occupational diseases or deaths in the last five years in the agroindustrial sector of the municipality of Santo Tomas, for What we can deduce is that there are many informal workers working in this sector, therefore, as they are not affiliated with the general occupational risk system, it is not possible to evidence ATEL reports in the occupational risk administrators.

In the context of the department of Atlántico, it is observed that there is no study of the psychosocial risks of workers in the agroindustrial sector of the municipality of Santo Tomás/Atlántico, for the period of the year 2023. This causes several causes to arise, among them What stands out is that the sociodemographic data of the workers in the agroindustrial sector of the municipality of Santo Tomas/Atlántico in the period 2023 is unknown, which according to Nucci and Morales (2009) The agroindustry in Colombia is one of the least explored economic sectors in the country. The available studies usually focus on very general levels of analysis, which makes it difficult to observe the particular and specific characteristics of this industry.

Likewise, the problem is caused because the psychosocial risk to workers in the agroindustrial sector of the municipality of Santo Tomas/Atlántico has not been technically evaluated in the period 2023; This is perhaps due to ignorance since in 2008, the Ministry of Social Protection of Colombia issued Resolution 2646, which established the obligations of employers in the country in relation to the prevention, diagnosis, intervention and control of the factors psychosocial risk in the work environment (Ministry of Social Protection, 2008). In 2010, in response to the need to use validated instruments specifically for Colombia, the Ministry commissioned the Pontificia Universidad Javeriana to create a series of tools that would meet this purpose (Ministry of Social Protection, 2010). Gómez, V (2016).

Furthermore, the effects of the workers in the agroindustrial sector of the municipality of Santo Tomas/Atlántico in the period 2023 are unknown and it must be taken into account that Psychosocial risk factors can be described as the situations to which employees are exposed in their workplace. workplace and that have the potential to have an adverse impact on your health, encompassing physical, social and mental aspects. These factors are closely related to the

individual characteristics of the workers and the environment that encompasses the personal, social and work-related (Polanco, 2017).

If the problem remains, the consequences for the agroindustrial sector of the municipality of Santo Tomas/Atlántico will increase, which are mentioned below:

Increase in accidents among workers in the agroindustrial sector of the municipality of Santo Tomas/ Atlántico in the period 2023, according to data provided by the Colombian Safety Council, in 2017, a fairly high accident rate was recorded in the agricultural sector. , reaching 15.89% per 100 workers. This percentage is significantly higher than in any other economic activity.

In addition, there is an increase in absenteeism among workers in the agroindustrial sector of the municipality of Santo Tomas/Atlántico in the period 2023, taking into account that work absenteeism is a global phenomenon of great relevance, which represents a serious challenge with broad implications in the social, economic and human spheres. This phenomenon affects three fundamental levels: the business, the individual and the social, as Ferro Soto, García Alonso and Lareo Lodeiro point out in their 2014 study. It is a problem that impacts the entire society, but its influence is particularly significant in companies, which justifies the need to be investigated and addressed, especially by organizations, since they are the ones that most directly experience the consequences of this phenomenon.

Likewise, the proposed analysis contributes to the symptoms in workers in the agroindustrial sector of the municipality of Santo Tomas/ Atlántico in the period 2023. The Ministry of Social Protection of Bogotá, in 2010, included in its list of occupational diseases those pathologies that They can arise as a result of stress in the work environment. In this context, several risk factors related to stress were identified, including the following aspects: job demands, which refer to the demands that work imposes on individuals; the level of control over the work, that is, the capacity that each person has to make decisions related to their work; leadership dynamics and social relationships in the workplace; and reward, which refers to the remuneration that workers receive for their contributions and efforts to benefit the growth of the organization.

Likewise, another consequence of the problem under investigation is the low productivity of workers in the agroindustrial sector of the municipality of Santo Tomas/ Atlántico in the period 2023.

Productivity can be considered as the result of the performance of personnel, who, when found in an environment that guarantees basic conditions of safety and well-being at work, can deploy their maximum potential to produce goods and services efficiently. In this sense, any effort aimed at improving productivity in an organization originates in people, as pointed out by Singh in 1998 and Cox and Rial-González in 2000. This reinforces the idea that managers must prioritize attention to human resources as its main objective in an organization.

Demotivation is also shown in workers in the agroindustrial sector of the municipality of Santo Tomas/ Atlántico in the period 2023, as Giraldo (2005) says. The results of harassment in the workplace are reflected in unmotivated and dissatisfied employees, who will perceive the work environment as hostile and associated with suffering, which will inevitably affect their performance in a negative way. Therefore, the general objective of this article is to determine the

psychosocial risks in workers in the agroindustrial sector of the municipality of Santo Tomás/Atlántico in the period 2023.

In the context of the growth of the informal economy and the importance of the agroindustrial sector in the municipality of Santo Tomás, Atlántico, the need arises to understand and address the psychosocial risks faced by informal workers in this sector. The theoretical study of these risks is presented as a fundamental component to identify working conditions and their implications on the mental health and well-being of workers. In this research framework, the main theories and models related to psychosocial risks in the workplace will be examined, as well as relevant previous studies that address this topic. Furthermore, the importance of this study in the local context of Santo Tomás, Atlántico, will be highlighted and the foundations will be established for empirical research that will allow a deeper and more specific understanding of the psychosocial risks in this particular context.

The research article: Workers' Health is found within the research background. Maracay-Venezuela (Delgado, L., Silveira, R. & Luna, J., 2016), which constitutes a relevant point in the research background, since it addresses the participation of the psychologist in the General System of Occupational Risks, a fundamental aspect in occupational health policy in Colombia. Given that this participation takes place in diverse environments with specific characteristics, the need for an appropriate methodological approach to understand the work of these professionals is recognized. In this sense, it was determined that the analysis of said work, with the objective of understanding it instead of judging it, required a different approach than surveys or structured interviews. Instead, it was decided to use conversations that, over several meetings, allowed the construction of narratives as analysis tools. This approach was considered more appropriate to capture the complexity of psychologists' experiences and practices in the workplace, thus allowing a deeper and more contextualized understanding of their work.

Likewise, as Nora H. Londoño (2010) says in her research article: Psychosocial and environmental risk factors associated with mental disorders (Colombia). The most common mental disorders, according to research, are depression and anxiety. Depression affects approximately 10-25% of women and 5-12% of men, while anxiety affects 3-5% of the general population throughout life (American Psychiatric Association, 2002). In Colombia, according to the National Mental Health Study carried out by Torres and Montoya (1997) with a sample of 2,100 participants, the prevalence of major depression was reported to be lower, with rates of 5-9% for women and 2 - 3% for men. However, a subsequent study in 2003 revealed that 14.9% of women and 8.6% of men had experienced a depressive episode at some point in their lives (Ministry of Social Protection, 2003).

Likewise, in their research article "Psychosocial factors at work (demand-control and effort-reward imbalance), mental health and blood pressure (Colombia)", Gómez and Moreno (2009) have developed advanced models to understand and anticipate the effects of Psychosocial Factors-Work (FPS-T) in health. Two of the most prominent models are the "Job Strain" or Demand-Control (D/C) model proposed by Karasek (1998), and the Effort-Reward Imbalance (DER) model by Siegrist and Peter (2000). These models are distinguished by their empirical support. However, it is important to note that most of the research on these models has been carried out primarily in developed nations, such as the United States and some European countries. Therefore, there is a

pressing need to conduct more representative studies using these models in the Latin American context, as the amount of research in this region remains limited. This will allow a more complete and contextualized understanding of the effects of SPF-T on the mental and physical health of workers in Latin America, specifically including Colombia.

As can be seen in the study *Psychosocial risk factors and job satisfaction in seasonal workers in Chile*, published in the journal *Panam Salud Pública* (2015), the degree of psychosocial risk was found to be high in two dimensions (presence of double working hours and work activity with growth opportunities), while it was moderate in the other areas; In contrast, job satisfaction was high in all dimensions. A negative correlation was observed between the perception of psychosocial risk factors and job satisfaction in three specific areas: work activity with development opportunities, social support in the work environment and quality of leadership, as well as compensation (except in the latter, regarding to satisfaction with the physical environment of the workplace). In conclusion, risks related to the seasonal nature of employment and the main aspects that workers consider influential in their job satisfaction and, therefore, in their general well-being were identified.

Likewise, Lina Lumbaqué (2021) Bogotá – Colombia, in her degree work *Risk factors in workers in the agricultural sector*, a bibliographic review mentions that six studies investigated exposure to psychosocial risk derived from stress, which arises from various factors such as emotional problems. production due to drought and financial difficulties, psychiatric disorders attributed to economic worries and feelings of personal failure, as well as a history of low education and dysfunctional family environments during childhood. Other factors identified include alcohol consumption, interpersonal conflicts, violence, feelings of hopelessness, lack of survival resources, and easy access to pesticides as a method of self-harm. In addition, the perception of work pressure, levels of job satisfaction and the lack of social support in both the work and family spheres were noted, resulting in significant exposure to this psychosocial risk.

In this sense, Sotomayor (2012) Chile, at the Inter-American meeting at the Ministerial Level in Health and Agriculture: Agriculture-Health-Environment: joining efforts for the well-being of the people of the Americas, points out that research on psychosocial aspects is less outstanding within the agricultural field. However, he highlights the presence of cases of diagnosed depression and reports of suicide among workers in the agricultural sector, which could be attributed to interruptions in labor production and the consequent loss of income for sustenance.

Therefore, as can be seen in the article: *The quality of work life in companies in the agricultural and agroindustrial sector* (Restrepo. F and López. A) 2016, Colombia, results of a research carried out in 12 companies in the agricultural and agroindustrial sector of the city of Medellín: *The quality of work life in Antioquia companies*, financed by the University of Antioquia and the Colombian Association of Labor Relations -Ascort-, shows *The most common symptoms and with the highest scores include "physical fatigue", "mental load", "back pain" and "muscle tension". On the other hand, the least frequent symptom and with the lowest score is "mistreatment of colleagues or clients."* In addition, the skewness and kurtosis coefficients were calculated, confirming that, in the case of all the factors analyzed, there is little uniformity and symmetry, which indicates a departure from the mean and a positive bias towards the highest scores.

As observed in the research article Hernández-Bello, A., Flórez-Flórez, J., and Suárez-Morales, Z. (2022) Health, work and capital: the case of women workers in the flower agroindustry Madrid, Colombia, 2019-2020, mention that the health problems that affect women employed in the Colombian flower agroindustry are persistent and shared together. These problems are a direct consequence of the working conditions of the sector and the requirements of the production process. By studying these problems from the perspective of women workers, we can understand them as lived experiences that reveal the multiple ways in which capital is accumulated and, at the same time, reflect an ethical-political commitment to the struggles of women working in the agroindustry of flowers.

Taking into account the SG-SST documentary proposal for a company in the agroindustrial sector in Villavicencio – Colombia (Diana Taborda 2023), in this context, employees express that work stress is triggered by the length of the working day. Following this, task conditions are identified as another contributing factor, followed by a minimal proportion attributing stress to organizational management. Finally, some members of the workforce claim not to be exposed to these types of psychosocial risks.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2016), mental health is influenced by social, psychological and biological factors. In this sense, continued socioeconomic pressures represent a risk to mental health at both the individual and community levels. Examples of indicators of this risk include poverty and low educational attainment. Likewise, the WHO (2016) establishes a relationship between "poor mental health" and situations such as rapid social changes, gender discrimination, social exclusion, stressful work environments, violence, physical health problems and human rights violations.

Materials and methods

This research is framed as a study with a quantitative approach, a transversal design, a descriptive field study. In this approach, it will be proposed to describe in a detailed and systematic manner the situation of psychosocial risks faced by workers in the agroindustrial sector in the Municipality of Santo Tomás, Atlántico, during the period 2023. The main objective is to document and understand the characteristics, magnitude and nature of the psychosocial risks present in this group of workers.

Descriptive research will generate a detailed overview of the psychosocial risks experienced by workers in this specific context. This approach will help identify problem areas, trends and patterns which, in turn, can serve as a basis for decision-making and the implementation of intervention strategies aimed at improving the psychosocial health of these workers.

To carry out this type of research, a representative sample of 60 informal workers from the agroindustrial sector of Santo Tomás, Atlántico, it was applied the instrument "Psychosocial Risk Assessment Questionnaire at Work." The instrument consists of a series of structured questions that address various dimensions related to psychosocial risks, such as work stress, workload, quality of work relationships, social support and other relevant factors.

The questionnaire was designed considering the specialized literature on psychosocial risks in the work environment and was validated to ensure its reliability and validity. The measurement scale used in the questionnaire allows participants to provide answers that reflect their perception of the psychosocial risk situation in their work environment. to a representative sample of workers in the agroindustrial sector. This survey includes questions related to various dimensions of psychosocial risks, such as work stress, workload, social support, among others. Through descriptive statistical analysis, such as frequency analysis and measures of central tendency, we will seek to summarize and present the data in a concise and clear manner.

Results and discussion

Once the research instrument is applied, we obtain the following results:

Table 1. Psychological demands. Can you do your work calmly and keep it up to date?

Psychological Demands	Always	Many times	Sometimes	only ever	Never
Can you do your work calmly and keep it up to date?	12	13	5	0	0

Fountain:own (2024)

41% of workers stated that they can do their work calmly and keep it up to date "Many times", while 20% indicated that they do it "Always". In addition, 17% responded that they achieve it "Sometimes", another 17% mentioned doing it "Only sometimes", and 5% admitted not being able to do it "Never". The survey results suggest that while most workers can do their jobs comfortably and keep up to date to some extent, there are still areas for improvement that need to be addressed to mitigate psychosocial risk in the workplace.

According to the survey conducted, 51% of workers indicated that they have to face difficult decisions at work "Sometimes." Furthermore, 25% stated that they never face these types of decisions, while 22% indicated that they do so "Many times." Only 2% mentioned doing it "Only sometimes", and no worker surveyed answered that they always have to make difficult decisions. The survey results suggest that making difficult decisions is a common part of the work experience for many workers, and employers must be attentive to their employees' needs and concerns in this regard to adequately manage psychosocial risk. Which can be represented in the following figure 1:

Figure 1. Psychological demands. In your job, do you have to make difficult decisions?

52% of workers indicated that their work produces emotional exhaustion "Only sometimes." Furthermore, 33% mentioned experiencing it "Sometimes", while 8% admitted feeling it "Many times". On the other hand, 5% stated that they never experience this emotional exhaustion, and only 2% reported feeling it "Always." Survey results indicate that emotional burnout is a common workplace problem for many employees, and employers should take steps to address it and promote a healthy and sustainable work environment.

48% of workers admitted to having to keep their emotions to themselves and not express them in their work "Only sometimes." Additionally, 30% indicated that they do it "Sometimes," while 15% stated that they never have to contain their emotions at work. On the other hand, 5% mentioned doing it "Many times", and only 2% indicated that they always have to keep their emotions to themselves. The survey results suggest that a significant proportion of workers face the need to contain their emotions at work, which may have implications for their emotional well-being and job performance. Employers should take steps to address this issue and promote a work environment that encourages authentic and healthy emotional expression.

According to the data collected, it appears that a large portion of workers require constant attention in their work. Specifically, 37% of respondents stated that their job demands constant attention "Always," followed by 30% who mentioned it "Sometimes," and 28% who experience it "Many times." Although only 5% reported it as "Only sometimes", it is relevant to note that no respondent answered that their job never requires constant attention. The survey results suggest that the need for constant attention is a common feature in respondents' work environment, highlighting the importance of addressing this aspect to promote employee well-being and productivity.

Based on the survey results, it appears that a significant portion of workers have influence over the amount of work assigned to them in their jobs. Specifically, 43% of respondents indicated that they have "Many times" influence on the amount of work assigned, followed by 33% who mentioned having "Sometimes" influence. Additionally, 12% reported having influence "Always" and another 12% reported it as "Only some of the time." It is notable that no worker surveyed answered that he never has influence over the amount of work assigned. The survey results suggest that a significant proportion of workers have influence over the amount of work assigned, which can have both positive and negative implications for workplace well-being. Employers should consider these dynamics when designing workplace policies and practices that promote a healthy and productive work environment. Which can be represented in the following figure 2:

Figure 2. Active Work and Skill Development. Does it influence the amount of work assigned to you?

Based on the information collected, it appears that most workers have the flexibility to temporarily leave their job to talk to a colleague. Specifically, 51% of respondents mentioned that they may do it "Many times," suggesting that this practice is common in the workplace. Additionally, 27% indicated that they do it "Only sometimes," while 20% reported it as "Sometimes." Although only a small percentage of workers (2%) responded that they never leave work to chat, it is notable that no respondents stated that they always can do so. The data suggests that most workers have the flexibility to temporarily leave their work to chat with colleagues, which may be indicative of a collaborative and communicative work environment.

Table 2. Active Work and Skill Development. Does your job allow you to learn new things?

Active Work and Skill Development	Always	Many times	Sometimes	only ever	Never
Does your job allow you to learn new things?	4	28	27	1	0

Fountain: own (2024)

46% of respondents stated that their job allows them to learn new things "Many times", indicating a significant frequency in acquiring additional knowledge and skills in the work environment. Furthermore, 45% mentioned that they do it "Sometimes", suggesting that the learning opportunity is present in a considerable proportion of work activities. Although a smaller percentage of workers (7%) answered that they always learn new things at work, and only 2% reported it as "Only sometimes", it is notable that no respondent stated that they never have the opportunity to learn new things. The data suggests that most workers have the opportunity to learn new things in their work, which is a positive aspect for their professional development and job satisfaction.

38% of respondents indicated that they find the tasks they perform important "Many times", suggesting that they value the relevance of their job responsibilities frequently. Furthermore, 25% stated that they always consider what they do important, reflecting a strong belief in the importance of their tasks. Although a smaller percentage of workers (20%) mentioned that they consider it important "Sometimes", and 17% reported it as "Only some of the time", it is relevant to note that no respondent answered that they never perceive the importance of the tasks they perform. . The

data suggests that most workers perceive the importance of the tasks they perform in their work, which can have a positive impact on their motivation and work engagement.

32% of those surveyed stated that they often feel that their company is of great importance to them, followed by 17% who indicated that they always feel this way. Additionally, another 17% mentioned feeling lonely sometimes, while 33% reported it sometimes. Although only a small percentage (1%) answered that they never feel that their company is important to them, it is notable that the majority of workers surveyed have some level of connection or appreciation towards the company they work for. The data suggests that most workers have some level of connection or appreciation toward the company they work for, which may be an important factor in their engagement and job satisfaction.

Table 3. Social Support in the Company and Quality of Leadership. Do you know exactly what tasks are your responsibility?

Social Support in the Company and Quality of Leadership	Always	Many times	Sometimes	only ever	Never
Do you know exactly what tasks are your responsibility?	14	26	fifteen	5	0

Fountain:own (2024)

44% of respondents indicated that most of the time they know exactly what their job responsibilities are. Furthermore, 23% stated that they are always clear about this. Although a smaller percentage of workers (25%) mentioned that they are only certain of their responsibilities sometimes, and 8% reported it as only a few times, it is notable that no respondents answered that they never know what their responsibilities are. The data suggests that most workers have a clear understanding of their job responsibilities more often than not, which may be an important factor in their productivity and well-being at work.

43% of respondents mentioned that they only find themselves in this situation a few times, followed by 34% who indicated that this happens sometimes. Furthermore, 18% stated that they find themselves in this situation most of the time, suggesting a significant frequency of disagreement with current working methods. Although a smaller percentage of workers (5%) answered that they never have to do tasks that they believe should be done in another way, it is relevant to note that no respondent stated that this always happens. The data suggests that there is a significant proportion of employees who experience discrepancies between their perceptions of how tasks should be performed and current working methods, which may have implications for efficiency and job satisfaction..Which can be represented in the following figure 3:

Figure 3. Social Support in the Company and Quality of Leadership. Do you have to do tasks that you think should be done differently?

20% of respondents indicated that they always receive help and support, while another 25% mentioned that they receive this assistance most of the time. Additionally, 32% reported that this happens sometimes, suggesting that help and support is provided with some regularity. Although a similar percentage of workers (20%) mentioned that they only rarely receive help and support, and a small percentage (3%) answered that they never receive it, it is notable that the majority of respondents reported receiving some level of assistance from part of his superiors. Most workers reported receiving some level of help and support from their superiors, suggesting that there is a general willingness on the part of line leaders to support their teams. However, there is still room to improve the consistency and availability of this assistance in some cases.

40% of respondents indicated that they most often help each other at work, suggesting a collaborative and supportive work culture. Additionally, 35% mentioned that this happens sometimes, while 23% stated that they always help each other. Although a small percentage of workers (2%) answered that they never help each other among colleagues, it is notable that no respondent reported that this practice occurs only a few times. Data suggests that mutual help between colleagues is common in the workplace, reflecting a collaborative and supportive work culture that can have positive effects on the work environment and team productivity.

41% of respondents indicated that most of the time their bosses resolve conflicts well, suggesting a reasonable degree of competence in this area on the part of line managers. Additionally, 25% stated that their bosses always resolve conflicts well, reflecting high confidence in superiors' conflict management skills. Although a smaller percentage of workers (32%) mentioned that this happens sometimes, and a small percentage (2%) answered that their bosses never resolve conflicts well, it is notable that no respondents reported that this happens only a few times. Data suggest that most employees perceive their managers to have adequate conflict resolution skills, which can contribute to a more positive work environment and organizational effectiveness. However, there is still room to improve conflict management in some specific situations. Which can be represented in the following figure 4:

Figure 4. Social Support in the Company and Quality of Leadership. Do your immediate bosses resolve conflicts well?

41% of respondents indicated that they only experience this worry a few times, followed by 22% who stated that they never feel this way. Furthermore, 20% mentioned that this happens sometimes, while 17% indicated that most of the time they are worried about this situation. Although no respondent reported always feeling worried about their job, it is notable that a significant minority of workers do experience some concern about it. The data suggest that worry about dismissal or contract non-renewal is a common experience for a significant portion of workers, although the frequency and intensity of this worry may vary. Employers must proactively address these concerns to maintain the emotional well-being and productivity of their workforce.

Table 4. Compensation Dimension. Are you worried about having your tasks changed against your will?

Compensation Dimension	Always	Many times	Sometimes	only ever	Never
Are you worried about having your tasks changed against your will?	0	6	eleven	twenty-one	22

Fountain:own (2024)

37% of respondents indicated that they never feel worried about this possibility, followed by 35% who mentioned that they only rarely experience this worry. Furthermore, 18% indicated that this happens sometimes, while 10% stated that most of the time they are worried about being changed tasks. It is notable that no respondent reported always feeling worried about this aspect. Although most employees are not constantly worried about being changed tasks against their will, concern about this aspect is common among a significant portion of the workforce. Employers must proactively address these concerns to maintain the well-being and productivity of their employees.

43% of respondents indicated that they only sometimes receive appropriate recognition from their superiors, suggesting a perception of a lack of recognition on certain occasions. Additionally, 18% noted that they only experience this lack of recognition a few times, while another 17% mentioned that they feel recognized most of the time. Although a similar percentage of workers (17%) stated that they always receive the recognition they deserve, and 5% answered that they never receive it, these results suggest that there is room to improve the perception of recognition from superiors. The data suggests that, while some employees perceive an adequate level of recognition from their superiors, there is still a considerable proportion who feel that this recognition is inconsistent or

insufficient. Leaders should take steps to improve the delivery of recognition in the workplace and ensure employees feel valued and appreciated for their contribution. Which can be represented in the following figure 5:

Figure 5. Compensation Dimension. Do my superiors give me the recognition I deserve?

44% of respondents indicated that sometimes household chores are left undone in their absence, suggesting some irregularity in the performance of these chores when they are not present. Furthermore, 33% mentioned that this situation occurs only a few times, indicating that on most occasions housework is carried out despite their absence. It is relevant to note that 23% answered that they are never left without doing these tasks, which suggests good organization or cooperation at home to guarantee their completion even in the worker's absence. Although no respondent stated that this occurs always or most of the time, these results indicate that, in general, there is some continuity in the completion of household tasks despite the absence of workers. The data suggest that, in general, there is some continuity in the completion of household tasks despite the absence of workers, which may indicate good organization and cooperation in the home. However, there is still a considerable percentage of occasions in which tasks are left undone, suggesting areas for improvement in the distribution of responsibilities and household planning.

43% of respondents indicated that they sometimes think about these demands while working, suggesting that these concerns may arise intermittently during their workday. Additionally, 35% mentioned that they only find themselves thinking about these demands a few times, indicating that they are mostly able to maintain focus on their work responsibilities. It is relevant to note that 20% answered that they never think about these demands while they are at work, which suggests an ability to separate work and home concerns. Although a small percentage (2%) said they always think about these demands, and none mentioned that this happens most of the time, these results reflect a variety of experiences regarding the ability to concentrate at work and manage worries. personal. The data suggests that employees have a variety of experiences in managing domestic and family demands while at work. While most are able to maintain focus on their work responsibilities, a significant proportion find that these concerns arise intermittently during the workday. Employers can help mitigate these concerns by creating a work environment that promotes work-life balance and effective stress management.

Which can be represented in the following figure 6:

Figure 6. Double Presence Dimension. When you are at work, do you think about domestic and family demands?

Likewise, the result of the averaged total of the psychological dimensions of the representative sample of 60 informal workers in the agroindustrial sector of Santo Tomas, Atlántico, in the following table 5:

Table 5. Psychological dimensions

Psychological demands	Active work and possibility of development	Social support in company	Compensations	Double presence
Half 9	Half 7	High 7	Half 4	Half 2

Fountain: own (2024)

Conclusions

Taking into account the qualification criteria of the Psychosocial Risk Assessment Questionnaire at Work, described in table 6:

Table 6. Qualification criteria for the Psychosocial Risk Assessment at Work questionnaire

Psychological dimensions	Risk		
	Low	Half	High
Psychological demands	From 0 to 8	From 9 to 11	From 12 to 20
Active work and possibility of development	From 0 to 5	From 6 to 8	From 9 to 20
Social support in company	From 0 to 3	From 4 to 6	From 7 to 20
Compensations	From 0 to 2	From 3 to 5	From 6 to 12
Double presence	From 0 to 1	From 2 to 3	From 4 to 8

Fountain: own (2024)

It is determined that the dimension qualification Psychological demands the risk is medium in the representative sample of 60 informal workers in the agroindustrial sector of Santo Tomas, Atlántico.

Likewise, the rating of the dimension Active work and possibility of development, the risk is medium in the representative sample of 60 informal workers in the agroindustrial sector of Santo Tomas, Atlántico.

Furthermore, the dimension rating Social support in a company, the risk is high in the representative sample of 60 informal workers in the agroindustrial sector of Santo Tomas, Atlántico.

Likewise, the rating of the dimension Compensations in companies, the risk is medium in the representative sample of 60 informal workers in the agroindustrial sector of Santo Tomas, Atlántico.

Also, the dimension qualification Double presence in a company, the risk is medium in the representative sample of 60 informal workers in the agroindustrial sector of Santo Tomas, Atlántico.

In conclusion, the analysis of the psychosocial dimensions in the agroindustrial sector of the municipality of Santo Tomás, Atlántico, has shed light on key areas that require attention and action by employers, authorities and other actors involved in the workplace.

There is clearly a delicate balance between the demands of work and the emotional well-being of workers, as well as the need for strong social support and fair compensation. However, this study also offers an invaluable opportunity to implement positive and meaningful changes. By addressing the psychological demands of work, improving development opportunities, and fostering a supportive environment and work-life balance, you can build a healthier, more productive work environment for everyone. It is essential that the results of this analysis be used as a guide for the implementation of policies and practices that promote the psychosocial well-being of workers. Only through a continued commitment to these improvements can we achieve a more prosperous and equitable work future for the agribusiness community in Santo Tomás, Atlántico.

Furthermore, it is important to note that psychosocial risk management in the agroindustrial sector is crucial to promoting a healthy and productive work environment. Employers should take steps to address the concerns identified in the survey and promote effective strategies to manage workplace stress, encourage work-life balance, and ensure appropriate recognition and support at work. This can contribute to improving the emotional well-being and job satisfaction of workers in the agribusiness sector.

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